

MICROSTRUCTURE, AGEING CHARACTERISTICS AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ALUMINIUM ALLOY (A201) REINFORCED WITH ALTEX FIBRE

J E Smith, V D Scott and M G Phillips
School of Materials Science
University of Bath, UK

ABSTRACT

A well consolidated composite consisting of aluminium alloy A201 reinforced with alumina-based (Altex) fibres has been fabricated by liquid metal infiltration. A strong bond between fibre and matrix was developed, as evidenced by the fact that Young's modulus matched 'Rule of Mixtures' predictions, although there were indications that the fibre had suffered mechanical damage during preform manufacture. The full potential of A201 alloy was not realised because much of its magnesium was absorbed by the fibre, resulting in the formation of θ' type matrix precipitates rather than the preferred Ω phase.

INTRODUCTION

There is much interest in aluminium-copper alloy A201 because of its high tensile strength after heat treatment, ~ 500 MPa, and elevated-temperature stability. These properties are associated with the formation of Ω precipitates on $\{111\}$ lattice planes which give a higher age-hardening response than θ'' and θ' on $\{100\}$ planes in the Al-4Cu system. There is also potential to enhance properties of A201 alloy further by the addition of ceramic reinforcements; for example, to increase the stiffness of the alloy, with little weight penalty, by incorporating continuous fibres. The prospects of achieving such benefit is investigated in the present paper, which describes the microstructure, ageing characteristics and mechanical properties of aluminium alloy A201 reinforced with an alumina-based fibre.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS AND COMPOSITE MANUFACTURE

The matrix alloy, A201, had the nominal composition aluminium-4.7wt% copper-0.3wt% magnesium-0.7wt% silver. The reinforcement was Altex fibre (Sumitomo Chemicals, Japan), a continuous fibre, 10-15 μ m diameter, of nominal composition 85wt% alumina and 15wt% silica; it was supplied on spools as tows consisting of 500 filaments.

The composite was fabricated using the method of liquid metal infiltration (LMI), as described by Shamsul et al [1]. First, a fibre preform was made by winding fibre tows up to 50 layers onto a steel core plate, 65mm x 45mm. Infiltration was carried out using an alloy melt temperature of 850°C, a pressure of 25 MPa, and with the preform and the die preheated to 700°C and 450°C respectively.

HEAT TREATMENT

Specimens cut from unreinforced alloy and composite, ~10mm x 10mm x 10mm, were solutionised by heating at 500°C for 6 hours, followed by 530°C for 18 hours and a cold water quench. The samples were then artificially aged at 170°C for times of up to 1000 hours. Samples were mounted in cold cure epoxy resin to prevent further ageing, and ground smooth using progressively-finer diamond compound. Microhardness tests were performed using a Leco M-400 machine with Vickers pyramid indenter; a load of 25gf was applied for a time of 15 seconds, 10 indents being measured for each condition.

MICROSTRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Polished specimens were studied by light microscopy to assess metal infiltration, fibre distribution and any second phases present, and image analysis attachment being used to obtain volume fractions of the constituents. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDS) was used to establish the composition of second phases. Specimens were prepared for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) by first cutting a 3mm diameter disc of thickness 0.5mm and then 'dimpling' both surfaces this was followed by ion beam thinning, a cryogenic stage being used to prevent further ageing of the specimen. Thinned samples of the composite and unreinforced alloy, in both the as-cast and peak-aged conditions, were examined in a TEM fitted with an EDS system.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Tensile testing was carried out on unreinforced alloy and composite samples in the as-cast and peak-aged conditions. The composite specimens were prepared with fibres parallel to the direction of testing. The test coupons were 65mm long with a gauge length of 35mm, width 6mm and thickness 3mm; aluminium end tabs were attached to prevent grip damage during testing. Strain gauges were bonded to the central section parallel to the loading direction. The tests were carried out on an Instron 1195 machine using a cross-head speed of 1mm/min. Fracture surfaces were examined by SEM.

RESULTS

MICROSTRUCTURE

Alloy

A back-scattered electron image of the as-cast alloy, Fig.1, shows a typical cast structure, with coarse grains, ~200 μm diameter and extensively cored, and coarse particles at the grain boundaries. Using EDS, the particles were found to be either CuAl_2 or a mixture of copper aluminium and iron. Image analysis indicated that ~7vol.% of second phase was present.

After solution treatment, the amount of CuAl_2 phase was reduced to ~1vol.%, and the coring was removed. Upon ageing at 170°C, the hardness was found to increase from ~100 HV to reach a peak of 160 HV after 7 hours treatment, Fig.2. TEM examination of peak-aged alloy revealed fine precipitates lying on {111} planes of the aluminium lattice, Fig.3. Diffraction analysis indicates that the precipitates were Ω phase [2]. Using an estimated foil thickness of 300nm, the precipitate density was deduced to be $\sim 10^{21}\text{m}^{-3}$.

Composite

A transverse section through as-cast composite, Fig.4, shows that infiltration of fibres by the liquid metal was good with a matrix porosity below 1 vol.%. The fibre volume fraction was 0.46 ± 0.03 , although the distribution of fibres was somewhat uneven. The mean grain size of metal matrix was ~200 μm , not noticeably different from that in unreinforced alloy. Coarse particles, identified by EDS as CuAl_2 , were present around fibres, which suggests that these metal regions were the last to solidify. TEM examination showed groups of fine precipitates lying on {100} lattice planes which were θ' phase. A micrograph of the fibre/matrix interface is shown in Fig. 5a. EDS data from the fibre, fibre/matrix interface and matrix, Fig. 5b-d, indicates that a small amount of magnesium has segregated to the surface of the fibre; no evidence was found, however, for the formation of second phases at the interface.

Solution treatment of the composite reduced the amount of second phase present. Ageing at 170°C produced an increase in matrix hardness, to reach a maximum of 150 HV after 2 hours treatment, Fig. 2. TEM studies revealed fine matrix precipitates lying on {100} planes of the aluminium lattice, diffraction analysis showing that they consisted of θ' and θ'' phase. The precipitate density was estimated to be much the same as found in unreinforced alloy, that is $\sim 10^{21}\text{m}^{-3}$. EDS data confirmed that there was segregation of magnesium at the fibre/matrix interface, although no evidence was found for the formation of any reaction phases at the interface; however, some coarse CuAl_2 precipitates were seen here.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Alloy

Stress-strain curves for as-cast and peak-aged alloy are given in Fig. 6a. Values for Young's modulus, yield stress and failure strain derived from the curves are collated in Table 1, averaged results of 6 tests with 95% confidence limits.

Table 1. Unreinforced alloy

Condition	Young's modulus (GPa)	Yield stress (MPa)	Strain at yield (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Strain to failure (%)
as-cast	75 ± 5	95 ± 5	0.15 ± 0.01	270 ± 5	14.5 ± 1.3
peak-aged	70 ± 5	290 ± 50	0.40 ± 0.10	450 ± 30	4.6 ± 1.2

Composite

Stress-strain curves for as-cast and peak-aged composite are given in Fig.6b. Both curves show a noticeable reduction of slope (arrowed), referred to as a 'knee-point' [3], occurring at a stress of 105 MPa for as-cast material and 190 MPa for composite in peak-aged condition; the corresponding strains were 0.10% and 0.15%. The tensile strength of the composite was found to increase from 270 MPa to 415 MPa after heat treatment, whilst the failure strains were not significantly different. Collated test data are given in Table 2; the values for stress at the knee-point are referred to here as yield stress, for reasons we shall give later. Examination of the fracture surface showed evidence of fibre pull-out and some matrix yielding, Fig.7. The presence of matrix metal adhering to the fibre surface is a measure of fibre/matrix bonding.

Table 2. Composite

Condition	Young's modulus (GPa)	Yield stress (MPa)	Strain at knee point (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Strain to failure (%)
as-cast	120 ± 15	105 ± 30	0.10 ± 0.01	270 ± 30	0.30 ± 0.10
peak-aged	145 ± 20	190 ± 15	0.15 ± 0.05	420 ± 60	0.40 ± 0.10

DISCUSSION

MICROSTRUCTURAL ASPECTS

The method of liquid metal infiltration (LMI) produced a well-consolidated composite consisting of A201 alloy and 46 vol.% of continuous alumina-based (Altex) fibres. The fibres were fairly evenly distributed throughout the composite and matrix porosity was less than 1 vol.%. Similar results have been obtained on other composite systems utilising Altex fibres [1]. It has further been shown that a small amount of magnesium in the alloy is an essential factor for producing well-infiltrated composites, an effect which has been attributed to improved wetting of the alumina fibres. This is evidenced by the presence of magnesium in the surface regions of the fibre, as revealed by EDS data, see Fig.5. Such studies have also indicated that less than 0.5 wt% magnesium may be adequate to enhance infiltration, a level not significantly different from that in A201 alloy.

Although the microstructure of the composite exhibited many features typical of a cast metal, such as coring in the metal grains and coarse second-phase particles, the two-stage solution treatment was found to reduce significantly these effects. Artificial ageing at 170°C increased the hardness of the matrix, from ~130 HV to 150 HV after treatment for 2 hours. Comparative heat-treatment studies on unreinforced alloy produced a greater hardness increase, from 120 HV to 160 HV, although this took 6 hours to develop. It was also noted that, as ageing proceeded, the composite matrix showed a much more significant fall-off in hardness than unreinforced alloy.

The reason for this may be seen in the corresponding microstructures. In unreinforced alloy the Ω -precipitation mode was evident which, as has been shown [4], produces a high age-hardening response and good long-term stability. In contrast, the precipitation mode in the composite was quite different and yielded, essentially, θ' -phase which is less effective and stable. The change in precipitate mode is considered to be related to the reduction in the level of magnesium in the matrix caused as a result of magnesium diffusion into the fibre. As a consequence the likelihood of Ω formation would be reduced and the proportion of θ' which is formed would be increased, as demonstrated in previous studies [4]. It was interesting to note that the density of precipitates in the composite was not significantly different from that in the alloy despite the presence of a high dislocation density associated with residual stresses in the composite.

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR

The stress-strain curves for the composites, whether in the as-cast or peak-aged condition, exhibited 'knee-points' where a reduction occurred in the slope. This behaviour is associated with the commencement of yield in the matrix [3]. In as-cast composite the yield stress closely matched that measured on as-cast alloy, ~100 MPa, and the corresponding strains were also similar. In the peak-aged condition, however, the yield stress of the composite was significantly lower than in the alloy, 190 MPa compared with 290 MPa. The probable reason is that the composite contained θ' matrix precipitates rather than Ω and, as is well known [4], the hardening response of θ' is less than Ω . as has also been evidenced by quoted proof-stress values of ~320 MPa and ~520 MPa for wrought alloys containing the respective precipitates [5]. The effect that residual stress would have upon yield stress measurements has been considered but its contribution is small, ~20 MPa [6], and would not account for the present observations.

We may compare Young's modulus for the composite, E_c , measured from the initial region of the stress-strain curves (below the knee-point) with values predicted using the 'Rule of Mixtures' (ROM), that is

$$E_c = E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f)$$

where E_f and E_m are Young's modulus for fibre and matrix respectively, and V_f is the fibre volume fraction. Substituting our experimental value for E_m of 70 GPa (see Table 1), the manufacturer's figure of ~210 GPa for E_f , and taking V_f equal to 0.46 then gives a value of 130 GPa for E_c , in close agreement with directly measured values when experimental scatter is taken into account. This indicates that fibre and matrix were contributing fully to the longitudinal modulus and that the interface bond was strong.

Considering the strength of the composite (σ_c), a ROM approach may again be used to calculate ideal values

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f)$$

where σ_f and σ_m are fibre and matrix strengths respectively. Using the manufacturer's value of 1.8 GPa for σ_f and 270 MPa for σ_m , as measured on as-cast alloy, we obtain a strength of 800 MPa for as-cast composite. In the peak-aged condition the predicted strength is 900 MPa. Both values, irrespective of thermal condition are significantly higher than the measured values of 270 MPa and 420 MPa. Since it has already been shown that the fibre matrix bond is strong, it must be presumed that the strength of the fibre was less than the manufacturer's value, probably no more than ~400 MPa. Loss of fibre strength of this order of magnitude has been reported

previously [7], and in the case of Altex fibre it has been argued [8] that most of the loss occurs when winding the preform rather than during liquid metal infiltration.

CONCLUSIONS

Liquid metal infiltration has been successfully used to make well-consolidated composite of aluminium alloy A201 reinforced with continuous Altex fibre ($V_f \sim 0.46$). A strong bond was developed between fibre and matrix, resulting in the Young's modulus of the composite achieving 'Rule of Mixtures' predictions. The strength of the composite suffered as a result of damage to the fibre when winding the preform. Heat treatment of the composite to give matrix peak hardness increased the yield stress and strength of the composite. However, it was found that θ' -type precipitates were formed in the composite matrix rather than the Ω -phase which characterises the unreinforced alloy. This was caused by a reduction in magnesium level in the alloy as magnesium diffused into the fibre, suggesting that a higher magnesium content in the alloy is required to achieve full potential of the composite matrix.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

To the EPSRC and DRA for support. British Crown Copyright 1995/DRA. Published with permission of the Controller of Her Britannic Majesty's Stationery Office.

REFERENCES

1. J. B. Shamsul, N. Jomin, R. S. Bushby, V. D. Scott, Fabrication, microstructure and ageing characteristics of aluminium alloy (6061) reinforced with Altex fibre, *RAMM*, Malaysia, 1994, 289-298.
2. B. C. Muddle and I. J. Polmear, The precipitate Ω phase in Al-Cu-Mg-Ag alloys, *Acta Metall.* **37**, 3(1989), 777-789.
3. M. R. Piggott, Load Bearing Fibre Composites, *Pergamon* (Oxford, 1980), 199-200.
4. S. Kerry and V. D. Scott, Structure and orientation relationship of precipitates formed in Al-Cu-Mg-Ag alloys, *Metal Science* **18**, June(1984).
5. I. J. Polmear, Light Alloys - Metallurgy of the light metals, *Edward Arnold* (London, 1989).
6. P. J. Withers, W. M. Stobbs, O. B. Pedersen, The application of Eshelby method of internal stress determination of short fibre metal matrix composites, *Acta Metall.* **37**, (1989), 3061-3084.
7. A. R. Chapman, S. M. Bleay, V. D. Scott, Influence of microstructure on the strength of Nicalon-reinforced aluminium metal-matrix composites, *J. Mater. Sci.*, **29**, (1994), 4523-4534.
8. A. S. Chen, R. S. Bushby, V. D. Scott, M. G. Phillips, A study of the mechanical properties and microstructure of fibre-reinforced aluminium alloy, *Royal Soc. Proc. A*, in press.

Figure 1. Squeeze-cast A201 alloy.

Figure 2. Effect of ageing time, at 170°C, on hardness of composite matrix and as-cast alloy.

Figure 3. Precipitates in peak aged alloy.

Figure 4 Squeeze-cast composite, transverse section.

Figure 5. Thin section of squeeze-cast composite.
 a. Fibre/matrix interface region, TEM.
 b. EDS from fibre.
 c. EDS from fibre/matrix interface.
 d. EDS from matrix.

Figure 6. Stress versus strain for tensile tests
 a. unreinforced alloy.
 b. composite.

Figure 7. Composite fracture surface.